

Chemistry of the Solute Movement in Nematodes. Theory of Diffusion of Solute, Design and Fabrication of Apparatus and Experimental Procedure

M. L. SOOD*

Department of Chemistry
and

M. L. SOOD

Department of Zoology, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004

Manuscript received 24 November 1988, revised 20 April 1989, accepted 2 June 1989

The theory of diffusion of solutes in nematode parasite is developed and used to derive formulae from which the integral diffusion coefficient (\bar{D}) can be determined. A mathematical relation employing Fick's law, i.e. $\bar{D} \beta_{\text{nematode}} t = \ln \Delta C_0 / \Delta C_f$ (where β_{nematode} is a constant characteristic of the nematode, the 'Nematode constant', t the time of diffusion in second and ΔC_0 and ΔC_f are the initial and final concentration differences between the solute and the nematode) is used to determine the nematode constant. A new diffusion apparatus has also been fabricated and experimental procedure described to determine β_{nematode} using dilute potassium chloride solutions. The method to determine \bar{D} from the above relation with any other solutes is explained.

A survey of literature shows that although many excellent accounts on various aspects of nematode are available¹⁻³ no proper attempt seems to have been made to understand the basic mechanism of diffusion of solute in nematode. Further, although the basic principles of diffusion in electrolytes and non-electrolytes in liquids have already been established⁴⁻⁸ these are seldom employed to understand the transport process occurring in a nematode. Recently, one of the authors has successfully developed two theories—one concerning the diffusion process in germinating seed⁹ and the other in pollen grain¹⁰, and it becomes very important to extend these to a living organism like nematode. Before such an extension is applied to a living system like the nematode, it is important to know whether diffusion occurs in such a biological system or not. There are now available positive evidences regarding transport of solute (s) in nematode¹¹⁻¹⁶ and thus the development of a theory for such a system becomes justified. Keeping in view the above facts, the present study was undertaken with the following objectives: (i) to develop the theory of a process for evaluating the diffusion (integral) coefficient in nematode, and (ii) to test the validity of the theory by conducting the appropriate diffusion experiments.

Theory: The following assumptions are made.

(i) The nematode membrane is porous in nature.

(ii) The nematode is considered free from 'osmotic shock' even in very dilute electrolytic and non-electrolytic solutions. (iii) The membrane of the parasitic nematode is assumed to be in a quasi-steady state during the experiment. This means that the flux of solute in the x -direction is the same at all points and at some fixed distance in the membrane and is represented as $J(t)$. This assumption is valid under normal conditions. (iv) Total volume of the nematode and that of the solution remain the same during diffusion. (v) Concentration gradient represented as $\frac{\partial C}{\partial X}$ is the driving force

and is given by Fick's first law as

$$J = -D \frac{\partial C}{\partial X} \quad (1)$$

It is assumed that the nematode is placed in a solution of known concentration. (vi) Not only the electrolyte/non-electrolyte is absorbed uniformly over the entire membrane surface but the parasite also exude material (employing the efflux of some inorganic ions, etc.).

Now let us consider that the nematode is placed in a solution of known concentration. Let V_1 , V_2 and V_3 are the volumes of the solution, parasite and of the membrane respectively. Let the concentrations of the solution surrounding the parasite

at any time be C_I and that in the parasite be C_{II} respectively; the initial concentration of the solution before diffusion commences is C_1 and that in the nematode is C_2 , i.e. $C_I = C_1$ and $C_{II} = C_2$ when $t = 0$ (Fig. 1). Once the flux of solute into the nematode starts there will be a change in the solu-

Fig. 1. Initial and final conditions in nematode.

tion concentration with time and this will proceed until steady-state conditions are established. Hence C_I changes to C_3 ($C_1 \neq C_3$) and C_2 changes to C_4 ($C_2 \neq C_4$) in time t . For simplicity C_2 is assumed to be zero in the parasite in our present treatment although it will not be exactly equal to zero and care must be taken to introduce the necessary correction term (s) for very accurate work.

The initial and final concentrations are shown in Fig. 1. It represents a nematode surrounded by an external solution whose volume is equal to that of the nematode. The shape as shown and drawn in no way does it represent the exact shape and size of any nematode. The diffusional resistance of the membrane is supposed to be equivalent to that of a cylinder of stagnant liquid of effective area available for diffusion, i.e. A and average effective pore length l . This assumption is quite reasonable, because the membrane of nematode has certain thickness and is porous in nature. Since the flux J varies with time, it is therefore written as $J(t)$. The changes in concentrations C_I and C_{II} with time can be written as

$$\frac{dC_I}{dt} = - J(t) \frac{A}{V_1} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dC_{II}}{dt} = J(t) \frac{A}{V_2} \quad (3)$$

On subtraction we get,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d(C_I - C_{II})}{dt} &= - J(t) \frac{A}{V_1} - J(t) \frac{A}{V_2} \\ &= - J(t) A \left(\frac{1}{V_1} + \frac{1}{V_2} \right) \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

where, A , as already defined above, is the effective area available for diffusion. If D is the diffusion coefficient then according to Fick's law,

$$J(t) = - D \frac{\partial C}{\partial X} \text{ independent of } x \quad (5)$$

It is to be noted that the negative sign in equation (2) indicates that the diffusion occurs from a region of higher to lower concentration.

Now if we define a integral diffusion coefficient $\bar{D}(t)$ which is averaged over the concentration range existing at a particular instant, then

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{D}(t) &= \frac{1}{C_I - C_{II}} \int_0^{V_I} D dC \\ &= \frac{1}{C_I - C_{II}} \int_{x=1}^{x=0} D \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial X} \right) dx \\ &= - \frac{1}{C_I - C_{II}} \int_0^1 D \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial X} \right) dx \\ &= - \frac{1}{C_I - C_{II}} \int_0^1 -J(t) dx \text{ due to eqn. (5)} \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{D}(t) &= \frac{J(t)}{C_I - C_{II}} \int_0^1 dx \\ &= \frac{J(t)}{C_I - C_{II}} (l) \\ \text{or } J(t) &= \frac{\bar{D}(t) (C_I - C_{II})}{l} \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

on substitution in equation (4),

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d(C_I - C_{II})}{dt} &= - \frac{\bar{D}(t) (C_I - C_{II}) A}{l} \left(\frac{1}{V_1} + \frac{1}{V_2} \right) \\ &= \frac{A}{l} \left(\frac{1}{V_1} + \frac{1}{V_2} \right) \left[- \bar{D}(t) (C_I - C_{II}) \right] \end{aligned}$$

This on integration between the initial and final conditions will yield,

$$\bar{D} = \frac{1}{\beta_{\text{nematode}} t} \ln \frac{\Delta C_0}{\Delta C_t} \quad (7)$$

where,

$$\beta_{\text{nematode}} = \frac{A}{l} \left(\frac{1}{V_1} + \frac{1}{V_2} \right) = \text{Nematode constant (8)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta C_o &= C_1 - C_2 \\ \Delta C_i &= C_3 - C_4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } \bar{D} &= \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t dt \left(\frac{1}{C_I - C_{II}} \right) \int_{C_{II}}^{C_I} D dC \\ &= \text{Integral diffusion coefficient (9)} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the diffusion coefficient obtained from these experiments is a double-average over concentration and time, and is defined as the integral diffusion coefficient. The nematode constant represented by β_{nematode} will be characteristic of the nematode and depends upon the effective area (A) and average pore length (l) of the membrane and upon the volumes V_1 and V_2 . Since it is not simple to determine either A or l in a membrane, this constant cannot be accurately estimated by direct experiment and, therefore, an indirect method is employed. This has been discussed in the later part of the paper.

Assumption of the steady state in the nematode :
We have from equation (7),

$$\bar{D} = \frac{1}{\beta_{\text{nematode}} t} \ln \frac{C_1 - C_2}{C_3 - C_4}$$

The quasi-steady state assumption as employed by Barnes¹⁷ for a porous diaphragm cell can be used also for nematode. According to this if $V_1 = V_2 = V$ (say) and $C_2 = 0$ equations (8) and (7) can be written as

$$\beta_{\text{nematode}} = \frac{2A}{lV} \quad (10)$$

and

$$\ln \frac{C_1 - C_2}{C_3 - C_4} = \bar{D} \beta_{\text{nematode}} t \quad (11)$$

hence,

$$\ln \frac{C_3 - C_4}{C_1 - C_2} = -\bar{D} \left(\frac{2A}{lV} \right) t$$

or

$$\frac{C_3 - C_4}{C_1} \exp \left(-\frac{2A\bar{D}t}{lV} \right) \text{ (for } C_2 = 0) \quad (12)$$

After the attainment of the steady state conditions when $t=t$, C_I becomes C_3 ($C_1 \neq C_3$) and C_{II} becomes C_4 ($C_2 \neq C_4$). Since $C_3 + C_4 = C_1$, it follows from equation (12) that

$$C_3 = \frac{C_1}{2} \left[1 + \exp \left(-\frac{2A\bar{D}t}{lV} \right) \right] \quad (13)$$

$$\text{and } C_4 = \frac{C_1}{2} \left[1 - \exp \left(-\frac{2A\bar{D}t}{lV} \right) \right] \quad (14)$$

These equations use the quasi-steady state approximation.

The rigorous solution for C_3 as proposed by Barnes¹⁷ is

$$\begin{aligned} C_3 = \frac{C_1}{2} \left[1 + \left(1 - \frac{\lambda^2}{180} \exp \left\{ -\frac{2DAt}{lV} \left(1 - \frac{\lambda}{6} + \frac{\lambda^2}{45} \right) \right\} \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \frac{\lambda^2}{2\pi^4} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^4} \exp \left(-\frac{4n^2\pi^2 Dt}{l^2} \right) \right] \quad (15) \end{aligned}$$

A similar expression was obtained for C_4 . The term λ in equation (15) represents the ratio of the volume of solution in the porous diaphragm disc (V_3) to that of the solution in the diffusion cell (V), i.e. $= V_3/V$ (cf $V_1 = V_2 = V$), and hence will be very small. When applied to nematode, λ again will be very small since it represents the ratio of the volume of solution in the membrane (V_3) to that of the solution in the diffusion cell (V_1). The terms $\lambda^2/180$, λ^2/π^4 and even $\lambda/6$ will be much less than unity, and we may conclude that any errors inherent in the quasi-state assumption are almost negligible.

Calibration of nematode :

From equations (7) and (8) we have

$$\beta_{\text{nematode}} = \frac{A}{l} \left(\frac{1}{V_1} + \frac{1}{V_2} \right) = \frac{1}{\bar{D}t} \ln \frac{\Delta C_o}{\Delta C_i} \quad (16)$$

β_{nematode} is a characteristic of the nematode and depends upon the effective area available for diffusion, the average effective pore length (l) and the volumes of the nematode (V_2) and the solution (V_1). The constant can be related to equation (7) with the integral diffusion coefficient, time (t) during which diffusion process has taken place and to the initial (ΔC_o) and final (ΔC_i) concentration differences. Since A and l cannot be accurately determined it is difficult to find β_{nematode} from these parameters by the use of equation (8).

An acceptable alternative method to estimate the nematode constant is by the use of equation (7) provided we know accurately the value of the integral diffusion coefficient (\bar{D}) in nematode for any suitable reference electrolyte. Diaphragm diffusion cell experiments use 0.1 M KCl (and more recently 0.5 M KCl) for which an accurate \bar{D} value is known from absolute methods. Therefore, our present method of determining a diffusion coefficient for nematode will also be relative, as with diaphragm cells, since it will also require the estimation of the nematode constant from integral diffusion coefficient of any suitable reference electrolyte.

KCl or NaCl were selected because in both these salts the ionic mobilities of the cations and anions are nearly the same. At 25°, the value of

diffusion coefficient⁴ at 1.2 mM in the case of KCl is $1.96 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, whereas that for NaCl at .61 mM is $1.576 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. For salt solutions which may be infinitely diluted ($\ll 1.2 \text{ mM}$ and 1.61 mM) these values of diffusion coefficients will approach their limiting values of 1.994×10^{-5} and $1.611 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the case of KCl and NaCl respectively. Now if one selects any such concentrations of either KCl or NaCl which are infinitely dilute so that their diffusion coefficients approach the limiting value at any standard value of temperature (say 25°) then the diffusion coefficient at one salt concentration will be nearly equal to the value obtained at the second concentration, the concentrations selected should of course be close to one another. Further, the time during which steady state conditions are established for any such two concentrations will also be nearly same. In other words, we can safely assume that the product of diffusion coefficients (integral) and time for such two dilute solutions will be nearly equal. Let these two concentrations be 0.1 and 0.2 mM, then on the basis of the above facts,

$$(\bar{D}t)_{0.1 \text{ mM}} \approx (\bar{D}t)_{0.2 \text{ mM}} \quad (17)$$

Now it is possible to estimate β_{nematode} by conducting diffusion experiments with 0.1 and 0.2 mM at 25° using nematode(s) of the same species and weight. These will then provide us two nearly equal values of β_{nematode} related to the initial and final concentrations, i.e.

$$(\beta_{\text{nematode}})_{0.1 \text{ mM}} = \frac{1}{(\bar{D}t)_{0.1 \text{ mM}}} \ln \left(\frac{\Delta C_0}{\Delta C_t} \right)_{0.1 \text{ mM}} \quad (18)$$

and

$$(\beta_{\text{nematode}})_{0.2 \text{ mM}} = \frac{1}{(\bar{D}t)_{0.2 \text{ mM}}} \ln \left(\frac{\Delta C_0}{\Delta C_t} \right)_{0.2 \text{ mM}} \quad (19)$$

Dividing equations (18) and (19) and applying the assumption i.e. equation (17), we will get,

$$\frac{(\beta_{\text{nematode}})_{0.1 \text{ mM}}}{(\beta_{\text{nematode}})_{0.2 \text{ mM}}} = \frac{\ln \left(\frac{\Delta C_0}{\Delta C_t} \right)_{0.1 \text{ mM}}}{\ln \left(\frac{\Delta C_0}{\Delta C_t} \right)_{0.2 \text{ mM}}} \quad (20)$$

$$\approx \beta_{\text{nematode}} \quad (21)$$

It is, however, to be noted that since β_{nematode} is the ratio of two constants at 0.1 and 0.2 mM, it will not represent the exact true constant although this will be quite close to it. Any small variation of β_{nematode} obtained from equation (21) will introduce similar small error in the determination of integral diffusion coefficient by the use of the value of β_{nematode} obtained from equation (21) but this will further be minimised when the integral values of diffusion coefficients (\bar{D}) will be converted to more fundamental differential diffusion coefficient (D) (a procedure whose detailed discussion will

be presented elsewhere) as was done in case of diaphragm cell experiments⁷.

Thus simply knowing the initial and final concentration differences ΔC_0 and ΔC_t for nematode at 25° using 0.1 and 0.2 mM KCl or NaCl it is possible to determine β_{nematode} from equation (20).

Once the nematode constant has been determined, equation (7) can be employed to find the integral diffusion coefficient for any solute. Further, since β_{nematode} is independent of temperature the value at 25° with KCl or NaCl can be safely used in diffusion experiments at different concentrations of solutes and at any other temperatures. Since nematode exude material (implying the efflux of some inorganic ions) the initial concentration of solute (C_2) will not be zero as assumed in the theoretical treatment, and, therefore, in precise experiments concentrations will be required for C_2 .

Experimental

Equation (7) can be used for determining the integral (average) diffusion coefficient (\bar{D}) of the parasite. In order to achieve this a parasite (*A. galli*) was taken in a specially designed apparatus (Fig. 2). The diffusion apparatus was completely filled and care was taken to avoid air-bubble formation during the filling process. The apparatus was designed in such a way that the conductivity cell remained properly immersed in the solution

Fig. 2. Diffusion apparatus.

containing the parasite. The filling process involved the introduction of the parasite and immediately the solution of known concentration from the tube was added after removing the stopper. The stopcock was kept opened during the process. The side-tube in which the stopcock was fitted, was kept slightly below in level to fill the tube first.

The stop-cock was then closed and during this whole procedure, no air bubble remained in the diffusion apparatus. The tube (connected to B-10 joint) was then slowly filled, and the stopper introduced carefully to avoid formation of air bubble. The whole diffusion apparatus was thermostated with the conductivity cell connected to a conductometer and the diffusion experiment timed from this point. The change in conductance during the different intervals of time was recorded during the diffusion process. It may be noted that the use of flame photometer for determining only Na⁺ or K⁺ ion concentrations can be safely used. In case of non-electrolyte, a small drop of the liquid can be removed from the tube (connecting B-10 joint) after certain time intervals and any physical property such as refractive index etc., can be determined. A standard curve of concentration versus conductance initially prepared was used for finding the concentration after the experiment was over. Final concentration of the solution can also be obtained by removing the solution carefully in a beaker and noting the conductance or refractive index or any other suitable physical properties and reading the concentration from the standard curve. In order to achieve higher accuracy, the resistance of the leads connecting the conductivity cell and the conductometer must also be taken into consideration. The initial and final conditions, before and after the diffusion process were as follows :

Solution C ₂ Parasite C ₁ (t=0)	Solution C ₃ Parasite C ₄ (t=t)
---	---

Once the concentrations are determined by the above procedure the equation,

$$\bar{D} = \frac{1}{\beta_{\text{parasite}} t} \left(\ln \frac{\Delta C_0}{\Delta C_t} \right)$$

can be easily employed to find \bar{D} .

In order to check the validity of equation (7), diffusion experiments with 0.0001 M NaCl were carried out at constant temperature using single nematode parasite *Ascaridia galli* of fowl. The diffusion apparatus had a volume of 10 ml. The experiment was carried out for about 3 h. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Since there was positive change in NaCl concentration, there is no doubt about the validity of equation (7) and thus can be safely employed for other nematodes or similar living systems.

In case there are N number of parasites (nematodes) the above equation may be modified as

$$\bar{D} = \frac{1}{N \beta_{\text{parasite}} t} \ln \frac{\Delta C_0}{\Delta C_t}$$

This will then give the diffusion coefficient for single nematode.

TABLE 1 - DIFFUSION DATA WITH 0.0001 M NaCl IN *A. galli* AT 28°

Time min.	Resistance × 10 ⁴ Ω
0	0.155
15	0.155
30	0.153
45	0.152
60	0.150
75	0.148
90	0.148
105	0.147
120	0.145
135	0.145
150	0.140
165	0.140

(After 10-12 h) (Constant for 5 h)

Effect of stirring : In order to avoid the absorption of solution on the membrane surface, the parasite and solution required proper stirring. The effect of stirring rate on the parasite constant can be established by the use of magnetic stirrers one moving in the solution and the other stirring below the parasites (Fig. 3). Therefore, for accurate results the optimum rate of stirring needs to be established during the process of diffusion.

Fig. 3. Position of stirrers in diffusion apparatus.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M. L. S.*) is thankful to his wife, Nishi, for her help and cooperation and also to his advisor Professor S. L. Chopra (Ex-Head, Department of Chemistry) for encouragement. The other author (M.L.S.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial help.

References

1. C. P. READ, "Biology of Parasites", Academic, New York, 1966.
2. T. VON BRAND, "Biochemistry and Physiology of Endoparasites", Elsevier, North Holland, 1979.

SOOD & SOOD : CHEMISTRY OF THE SOLUTE MOVEMENT IN NEMATODES. THEORY OF DIFFUSION *etc*

3. J. BARRETT, "Biochemistry of Parasitic Helminths", MacMillan, Hong Kong, 1981.
4. H. S. HARNED and B. B. OWEN "The Physical Chemistry of Electrolyte Solutions", Reinhold, New York, 1957.
5. R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, "Electrolyte Solutions", Butterworths, London, 1959.
6. M. L. SOOD, and S. L. CHOPRA, *Indian J. Technol.*, 1975, 13, 329.
7. M. L. SOOD and B. MADHU, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1982, 27, 1239.
8. M. L. SOOD and P. C. KRISHANA, *Natl. Acad. Sci.*, 1985, 31.
9. M. L. SOOD, *J. Seed Sci. and Technol.*, 1987, 15, 1255.
10. M. L. SOOD, *Ann. Bot.*, 1988, 62, 481.
11. R. CAVIER and J. SAEVÉL, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Biol.*, 1951, 33, 447.
12. N. F. WEATHERLY, M. F. HANSON and M. C. MOSEN, *Am. J. Vet. Res.*, 1963, 25, 1206.
13. G. CASTRO and D. FAIRBAIRN, *J. Parasit.*, 1969, 55, 13.
14. R. G. BRUCE, *Proc. Br. Soc. Parasit. Parasitol.*, 1976.
15. R. D. LUMSDEN, *Exp. Parasitol.*, 1975, 37, 267.
16. P. W. PAPPAS and C. P. READ, *Exp. Parasitol.*, 1975, 37, 469.
17. C. BARNES, *Physics*, 1934, 5, 4.